

Characterizing Accuracy and Precision of Range Code-based GNSS-R Altimetric Observations Using Spire DDMs over Sea Ice

Jiahua Zhang, Jan-Peter Weiss, and John J. Braun

Abstract—Global Navigation Satellite System reflection (GNSS-R) signals can be leveraged to measure reflecting surface height. However, the code-based altimetric retrievals present biases that vary across reflection tracks, whose origin and nature remain unclear. This study utilizes Spire Global Inc.’s delay Doppler maps (DDMs) of GPS L1CA, GAL E1C, and BDS B1C reflection signals over sea ice to characterize the variation of biases and the precision of height retrievals. Employing data pairs of the same reflection signals collected by different antennas on a receiver, we observe that the height retrievals agree well to each other with similar biases from the mean sea surface (MSS) model. Height biases of the same transmitter and receiver also vary across acquisition time. Moreover, based on abundant reflection data over Hudson Bay, the height biases of different combinations of GNSS system and receiver follow normal distributions. After examining bias magnitude versus SNR, smaller biases can be observed at higher SNR levels. As for precision, it is generally on the order of meter to submeter for all GPS, GAL, and BDS height measurements, and improves with SNR, demonstrated by the same retrievals over Hudson Bay. GAL and BDS retrievals have similar precision from ~ 1.0 m at a SNR of 3 dB to ~ 0.5 m at 13 dB, better than that of GPS from ~ 1.5 m to ~ 0.5 m over a similar SNR range. The better precision of GAL and BDS retrievals can be attributed to narrower waveforms and finer DDM delay resolutions. A root mean squared difference (RMSD) of 0.83 m can be achieved between the averaged bias-corrected height observations of all GNSS systems and receivers and the MSS over Hudson Bay. Our study contributes to understanding the randomly varying height biases and designing instruments to facilitate accurate and precise altimetric observations.

Index Terms—GNSS reflectometry, GNSS-R, altimetry, delay Doppler map

I. INTRODUCTION

GLOBAL Navigation Satellite System reflection (GNSS-R) signals carry the information of time delays that navigation signals take to travel from the transmitter to the specular reflection point (SP), then to the receiver, which facilitates measuring the reflecting surface height in aid of the known positions of the transmitter and the receiver [1] (Fig. 1). GNSS-R altimetric observations can complement traditional monostatic radar and lidar altimetric measurements to fill their spatial and temporal sampling gaps. Ground tracks of reflection signals are approximately randomly distributed; and they can cover the areas that are not in the view of conventional altimeters, for example, the gaps between adjacent ground tracks and polar regions due to orbit inclination [2]. Moreover, GNSS-R can offer measurements day and night in all weather conditions, attributed to the inherent nature of L-band signals.

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Fig. 1. (a) presents a schematic diagram of GNSS-R altimetry, i.e., using the reflection signal to measure the reflecting surface height. e represents the satellite elevation angle, and ΔH stands for the reflecting surface’s ellipsoidal height. (b) The specular reflection and its model can be presumed to be parallel to be each other to simplify the calculation of ΔH from their difference $\Delta\rho$.

Delay Doppler maps (DDMs) of reflection signals record reflection signal power in the time and Doppler frequency domains, derived by cross correlating the received signal and the signal model. They are routinely collected by nearly all GNSS-R missions, such as TechDemoSat-1 (TDS-1) [3], CYGNSS [4], FengYun-3 [5], and Spire [6]. DDMs are usually used to monitor changes in soil moisture and ocean surface wind [7], [8], [9]. However, multiple studies have evaluated the feasibility and performance in extracting time delays from DDMs to conduct altimetric applications, such as over oceans [10], ice sheets [11], and inland water bodies [12], though the involved missions are not meticulously designed for altimetry.

The precision of range code-based altimetric measurements is relatively coarse, on the order of meter to submeter. For instance, based on CYGNSS DDMs, [13] measured sea surface height over the Seas of Indonesia with a precision of several meters, and [12] obtained inland water surface height retrievals with a precision of ~ 1.5 m during periods of mild solar activity. Their dominant error sources include the coarse

DDM delay resolution of ~ 0.25 chips (equivalent to ~ 75 m), which introduces significant uncertainty in estimating specular reflection delays, and the use of single-frequency observations, which precludes dual-frequency ionospheric correction. Limited antenna frontend bandwidth is another source of error, as it leads to rounded waveform peaks that reduce ranging precision. A wider bandwidth not only sharpens waveform peaks but also enables capturing wideband signals such as Galileo (GAL) and BeiDou Navigation Satellite System (BDS) signals with BOC modulations, whose waveforms are narrower and steeper than those of GPS L1CA signals. Leveraging these advantages, [14] achieved an overall agreement of ~ 0.5 m between ocean surface height retrievals and collocated radar observations at 5 km resolution using dual-frequency DDMs of GPS, BDS, and GAL signals with a delay resolution of ~ 3 m, further improving to ~ 0.2 m after averaging to 40 km resolution.

Carrier phases facilitate the high precision altimetry on an order of several centimeters [15], [16], however, it requires sufficiently coherent signals, for example, those over inland water bodies, sea ice, and coastal oceans [17], [18]. On the other hand, carrier phase-based altimetric retrievals are typically ambiguous due to the loss of coherence and cycle slips. Several studies have utilized the carrier phase observations to measure river slope, sea ice, ocean surface topography, icesheets elevations etc. [19], [20], [21], [22]. Code-based range observations are usually needed to mitigate the ambiguity of carrier phase observations.

Enhancing the accuracy and precision of code-based altimetry serves two purposes: providing a reliable reference for high-precision phase altimetry, and extending observational capability to difficult environments unfavorable for coherent reflection signals. However, a few studies have reported that code-based GNSS-R altimetric retrievals present biases varying among tracks (e.g., [10]), whose nature and origin remain unclear. Furthermore, as newer satellites collecting DDMs of multiple GNSS signals with finer delay resolutions become available, a systematic evaluation of the resulting precision enhancement is needed.

Spire Global Inc. has launched multiple batches of GNSS-R receivers equipped with relatively wider bandwidth antennas therefore can receive L1-band GPS, GAL, and BDS reflection signals over the globe. DDMs of BDS and GAL signals have finer delay resolutions than GPS DDMs as detailed in section II. Using Spire DDMs, this study compares height retrievals of the same GNSS reflection signals but captured by different antennas mounted on the same receiver to characterize the track-wise biases in terms of GNSS systems and receiver antennas. Abundant Spire data over Hudson Bay are used to assess the statistical features of biases and their changes with signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Reflection data over Hudson Bay are also used to evaluate the precision of height retrievals and characterize its dependence on signal modulation, DDM delay resolution, and SNR. Spire DDM data over sea ice-covered regions are focused because of their high prevalence of high SNR data [23].

Section II describes Spire DDM observations and their metadata for recovering reflection time delays. The method-

TABLE I
BASIC INFORMATION OF SPIRE GNSS-R RECEIVERS

Parameter	FM146 & FM147	FM172
Launch time	Jan 2021	Apr 2023
Orbit altitude (km)	530	480
Orbit inclination	98°	97°
Reflection antennas	3 × LHCP	
Antenna gain (dB)	8	10
GNSS signals	GPS L1CA (BPSK), GAL E1C & BDS B1C (BOC)	
# of delay bins	9	
Delay bin size (chips)	0.1 (BOC)	0.2 (BPSK)
# of Doppler bins	5	
Doppler bin size (Hz)	156.25	

ology of retracking specular reflection delays from DDMs and inverting altimetric retrievals is elaborated in Section III. Results and discussion are presented in Section IV. This study is then concluded in Section V.

II. SPIRE DELAY DOPPLER MAPS

This study uses the DDMs collected by the Spire Batch-2 satellites of FM146 and FM147 and the Batch-3 satellite of FM172 from January to July 2024. These Spire data were obscured under the NOAA Commercial Data Program (CDP), which have been evaluated to map soil moisture [8] and sea ice extent [23]. Each Spire satellite is equipped with three left-hand circular polarization (LHCP) antennas to receive L1-band reflection signals transmitted from multiple GNSS systems, including GPS L1CA, GAL E1C, and BDS B1C signals. Table I lists the basic information of these receivers, such as launch date, orbit height and inclination, and antenna gain.

Spire DDMs have 9 delay bins and 5 Doppler bins. However, the size of a delay bin is ~ 0.2 chips for GPS L1CA signals, whereas ~ 0.1 chips for GAL E1C and BDS B1C signals, as exemplified by the waveforms shown in Fig. 2. A waveform refers to the reflection signal power in delay bins crossing the DDM peak. Initially generated DDMs onboard satellite have 16 delays and 65 Doppler bins, however, they are cropped to a smaller size to reduce the data volume for the convenience of downlinking. The cropping parameters are recorded as part of the DDM metadata. A Spire DDM is produced by cross correlating the incoming reflection signal and the modeled signal, which is created using an open loop model to predict the Doppler shift and time delay based on the positions and velocities of the transmitter and the receiver over an Earth model [24].

The DDM-associated metadata offer the positions of the transmitter, SP, and the receiver and receiver clock errors, which are also necessary for recovering and modelling reflection delays. Moreover, Spire also provides quality flags to indicate the occurrence of anomalies in satellite attitude, signal tracking, calibration, and radio frequency interference (RFI), etc. These flags are also used to create a binary quality pass indicator. This study uses the DDMs passing the quality requirement.

Fig. 2. (a) illustrates the observed and simulated waveforms of GPS L1CA reflection signals. The SNR and the residual delay in range are presented as well. Similarly, (b) and (c) show the waveforms of GAL and BDS reflection signals.

III. METHODOLOGY

The height of reflecting surface over the Earth model, denoted as ΔH (Fig. 1), can be inverted from the difference between the observed reflection range (ρ_o) and the modeled one (ρ_m) as shown in the following equation:

$$\Delta H = \frac{\rho_m - \rho_o}{2 \sin e}, \quad (1)$$

where e stands for the signal elevation angle. Introducing the modeled reflection range ρ_m can effectively reduce the complexity of inverting reflecting surface height [13].

The observed reflection range ρ_o can be recovered from the open loop model parameters (ρ_o^{OL}), DDM cropping parameters (ρ_o^{CROP}), and the residual delay from the open loop model (ρ_o^{WF}), expressed as:

$$\rho_o = \rho_o^{OL} + \rho_o^{CROP} + \rho_o^{WF}. \quad (2)$$

The DDM metadata provides the former two parameters, ρ_o^{OL} and ρ_o^{CROP} . The residual delays ρ_o^{WF} can be derived from waveforms through retracking methods, i.e., identifying the specular reflection delay points on the waveforms. The specular reflection delay point varies on the leading edge of waveform with respect to the signal coherency. For a purely coherent signal, its waveform is symmetric around the peak at which the specular reflection delay point is located. However, for a noncoherent signal, the specular reflection delay is at a point with a fraction of the peak, e.g., $\sim 70\%$ of the peak for incoherent GPS L1CA signals [25]. This study employs the retracking method of fitting the waveform model to the observation to determine the specular reflection delay point. This retracking method relatively outperforms other methods, demonstrated in studies of assessing CYGNSS reflection signals for ocean altimetry [10], [25].

The VZ2018 model is utilized to simulate reflection waveforms which considers both coherent and incoherent reflection rays following the Kirchoff approximation [26]. The open-source software of WavPy implements the VZ2018 model and have been utilized in previous research [27]. For any given waveform observation, the corresponding coordinates and velocities of the transmitter and the receiver are fed into the software of WavPy to simulate waveforms with a spectrum of surface roughness. Those simulated waveforms are then compared to the observed one to find the best fit. The specular reflection delay point of the best-fit waveform is then used as

ρ_o^{WF} . Note that waveform observations are firstly up-sampled by a factor of 100 using the Whittaker-Shannon method [28], e.g., enhancing the delay resolution from 0.2 chips to 0.002 chips for GPS L1CA DDMs, to facilitate a finer determination of residual delays [12]. To avoid interpolation artifacts, a threshold of SNR of 3 dB is adopted heuristically. Figure 2 shows the waveform simulations that fit to the waveform observations best, and their retracted ρ_o^{WF} are shown as well.

The modeled reflection range can be expressed as

$$\rho_m = \rho_m^{GEOM} + \rho_m^{IONO} + \rho_m^{TROP} + \rho_m^{GEOP}. \quad (3)$$

Modeling reflection ranges has been detailed in [12]. A brief description is presented as follows. We first use the coordinates of the transmitter and the receiver to estimate the SP over the DTU mean sea surface (MSS) model [29] and then calculate the reflection range ρ_m^{GEOM} . For modeling ionospheric effects ρ_m^{IONO} , the UQRG global ionospheric maps (GIM) of total electron content (TEC) are used to estimate the ionospheric delays of reflection signals [30]. When estimating ionospheric delays for the reflection path from SP to LEO receiver, the TEC maps are scaled to the height of LEO receivers using the International Reference of Ionosphere (IRI) model [31]. The tropospheric delays ρ_m^{TROP} are predicted by using the VMF3/GPT3 model [32]. Reflection range errors due to the geophysical effects ρ_m^{GEOP} , including solid earth tides, ocean tides, polar tides are also modelled using the Python-based tidal prediction software (pyTMD) [33].

Spire reflection data are processed track by track to derive the altimetric retrievals. The DTU MSS model serves as the reference to validate our Spire retrievals. Sea ice freeboard thickness, i.e., sea ice elevations with respect to the MSS, are also considered to correct our height retrievals. We generate monthly sea ice elevation maps with a grid size of 0.25 degrees using the ICESat-2 ATL07 product of sea ice height [34]. Such maps of sea ice elevations suffice evaluating Spire retrievals due to their limited magnitudes on the order of a few centimeters to decimeters, significantly smaller than the variation range of biases and precision of Spire retrievals.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Coincident tracks of the same GNSS reflection signals captured by different antennas on a receiver

Reflection signals from a GNSS transmitter are often captured by different antennas of a receiver. Given the same

Fig. 3. Examples of coincident reflection data pairs of GPS PRN15, GAL PRN09, and BDS PRN42 in Baffin Bay collected by two antennas, Ant-02 and 04, mounted on FM172 on day of year 39 in 2024. Their SP locations color-coded with sea ice concentration, mean elevation angles, mean height biases from the MSS model, bias-corrected height retrievals, and SNR are presented.

transmitter and the receiver, these reflection signals propagate along nearly the same paths, thus, having similar ionospheric and tropospheric errors. Moreover, the errors associated with the transmitter and reflecting surface are also similar. The consistency in altimetric retrievals between those coincident tracks can indicate the impact of receiver antenna and other factors involved in signal acquisition and processing.

Three pairs of coincident tracks are presented in Fig. 3 as examples, which are of GPS L1CA, GAL E1C, and BDS B1C over Baffin Bay near Greenland collected by two different antennas, i.e., Ant-02 and 04, of FM172 on the hour of $\sim 6:00$ UTC, day of year (DOY) 39 in 2024. These three pairs of tracks are nearly collocated. Regarding the pair of GPS signals, they have a mean elevation angle of 55.6° . The height retrievals of Ant-02 and Ant-04 have similar variation

trends, which also agree well with the MSS model. The height biases of these two tracks are comparable, which are 6.54 m and 5.92 m, respectively. The unbiased height retrievals show positive deviations from the MSS over the area from -73° to -71° in longitude. This could be due to errors in ionospheric impact modeling and other errors overlooked in this study. Furthermore, relatively smoother height observations can be observed when reflection signals have higher SNR, for instance, from -79° to -78° and from -73° to -71° in longitude. This is consistent with the finding that higher height precision correlates with higher reflection SNR, presented in the following section IV-B.

Regarding the tracks of GAL signals, we can observe the similarity in their height variations from two different antennas. The height retrievals of both tracks agree well

Fig. 4. (a) shows the track-wise height biases of all reflection data pairs. (b) illustrates a histogram of the difference in height biases within each reflection data pair. (c) presents the density scatter plot between bias-corrected retrievals of coincident tracks within each pair. (d) Height biases of reflection data pairs for GPS PRN04, 06, 15, and 23.

to the MSS model generally with comparable biases of ~ -8.00 m. Positive deviations also can be found at the end of tracks around the longitude of -72° . GAL-based height retrievals are much smoother than those GPS results, though their SNR are comparable. This should be due to the narrower waveforms of GAL signals of BOC modulations and better DDM delay resolutions than GPS signals, which is discussed in the section IV-B. Retrievals of the BDS signals are similar to GAL signals in terms of their agreement to the MSS and smoothness. However, the BDS-based height retrievals do not show deviations from the MSS as significant as those from GPS and GAL signals near the longitude of -72° . Further analysis will be conducted to investigate the causes.

89 pairs of coincident tracks over sea ice are processed to derive their track-wise biases, i.e., the mean bias along the track, as shown in Fig. 4a. Height biases vary significantly within a range of ~ 50 m. For each pair of tracks, similar height biases can be observed for signals transmitted from either GPS, BDS, or GAL. The difference between height biases within each pair follow an overall normal distribution with a mean of 0.05 m and a standard deviation of 0.53 m (Fig. 4b). These difference of height biases could be attributed to the baseline between antenna phase centers and other instrument factors. After correcting for height biases, the altimetric retrievals of coincident tracks agree well with high correlation coefficient for all GNSS systems, as shown in Fig. 4c. Comparable height retrievals of the same GNSS reflection signals collected by different antennas indicates that

the receiver antenna exerts minor impact on the magnitude of track-wise biases. Moreover, the magnitude of height bias for the same GNSS transmitter and the receiver varies across acquisition time, as demonstrated by Fig. 4d illustrating the variations in height biases for GPS PRN04, 06, 15, 23 with at least 5 pairs of tracks individually.

B. Reflection signals over Hudson Bay

Reflection signals from Feb to Jun 2024 in Hudson Bay are utilized to conduct a more comprehensively statistical analysis of track-wise biases and precision of height retrievals. Figure 5a shows the spatial distribution of all reflection tracks and their magnitude of altimetric retrievals. For any given track, we compute its mean bias from the MSS model. The bias-corrected height retrievals are depicted in Fig. 5b. Those retrievals are then gridded and averaged to drive a map of 0.25 degrees shown in Fig. 5c. Compared with the MSS model shown in Fig. 5d, we can observe a good agreement, i.e., higher surface height in the northeast and lower in the southwest. Figure 5e presents a density scatter plot between gridded unbiased Spire retrievals and the MSS model, showing a strong correlation with a correlation coefficient of 0.98 and an overall RMSD of 0.83 m.

The histogram of track-wise biases over Hudson Bay is presented in Fig. 6a, which generally follows a normal distribution with a mean of 0.12 m and a standard deviation of 6.78 m. When showing the track-wise biases with respect to

Fig. 5. (a) and (b) shows the original and bias-corrected Spire height retrievals, respectively. (c) presents the gridded maps of unbiased height retrievals. (d) shows the MSS height. (e) A density scatter plot between gridded unbiased Spire height observations and the MSS model.

the mean SNR of tracks, we can observe that the variation range becomes smaller when the SNR is getting larger. This indicates high gain antenna could be helpful for obtaining retrievals with smaller biases. We also show the histograms of track-wise biases for each GNSS system and Spire receiver in supplement. Similarly, the track-wise biases for each pair of transmitter system and receiver follow normal distributions.

We then examine the dependence of height precision on SNR. For a long track of data, SNR changes due to surface property variations, e.g., sea ice concentration and snow wetness. Any given track of data is divided into segments of 10 samples. Then the standard deviation of the difference between retrievals and the model is then computed to represent the precision of that segment. The mean SNR is also calculated for each segment of that track.

Figure 7 shows the precision of altimetric heights of different GNSS systems at different SNR levels. For GPS signals, the precision magnitude is better than 3 m for most retrievals.

The mean precision is around 1.5 m at relatively low SNR of 3 dB and becomes better with SNR gradually. The precision can reach ~ 1 m at the SNR level of 9 dB and ~ 0.5 m at the SNR of ~ 15 dB. GAL and BDS reflection signals have relatively better precision. Their precision can achieve 1.0 m even at relatively low SNR (e.g., 3 dB) and becomes smaller with higher SNR. Moreover, GPS, GAL, and BDS signals have similar magnitude of precision at high SNR levels, e.g., larger than 10 dB. Narrower waveforms and higher delay resolutions should be the reason why GAL and BDS outperforms GPS signals in terms of precision at relatively low SNR levels. At higher SNR, reflection signals tend to be highly coherent, the specular reflection delay point is nearly at the peak of waveform, leading to similar ranging precision of GPS, GAL, and BDS signals.

Fig. 6. (a) shows the histogram of track-wise biases of reflection data over Hudson Bay. (b) depicts a scatter plot between track-wise biases and mean SNR.

Fig. 7. Variations of the height retrieval precision with respect to SNR for GPS, GAL, and BDS signals.

V. CONCLUSION

Spire range code-based altimetric retrievals present randomly varying track-wise height biases, demonstrated by the normal distribution of height biases of different GNSS systems and receivers. Comparable track-wise biases of the same reflection signals collected by different antennas on the same receiver implies that the antenna could not be the cause for biases. The biases of height retrievals can be reduced with higher SNR. As for the height precision, it can be enhanced as well with higher SNR data for both BPSK GPS signals and BOC GAL and BDS signals. Moreover, GAL and BDS retrievals systematically have better precision than GPS ones, which should be due to narrow waveforms and finer DDM delay resolutions. The height precision can achieve 0.5 m at a SNR higher than around 13 dB. This indicates the necessity of instrument design to collect high SNR data to achieve accurate and precise GNSS-R altimetric applications.

Height biases could be partially due to the penetration depth of GNSS reflection signals into snow and sea ice and the ionospheric impact modeling. More efforts are required to study the interaction between L-band signals and snow/ice and its regulation on the effective reflector depth of GNSS signals. Dual frequency-enabled missions, e.g., HydroGNSS [35] collecting L1 and L5 GPS and GAL signals, can help mitigate ionospheric impact.

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Supplement

Figure S1: Histograms of height biases of different combinations of GNSS systems and Spire receivers over Hudson Bay.